

Applying a Genetic Algorithm for Sequencing Optimization in a Mixed-Model Manufacturing Assembly Line

Olli Niemitalo, Genrikh Ekkerman, Olli Koskela, Jukka Pulkkinen
Häme University of Applied Sciences

ABSTRACT

In this study, we provide a genetic algorithm for the sequencing of made-to-order products in a mixed-model assembly line. Such assembly lines, in which similar products are assembled with customizations, are widely used in the manufacturing industry. An assembly line typically consists of several assembly stations that can be manual or automated. In each station, differences between consecutive products may require changing of tools or part pallets located next to the station, with an associated idle time cost away from actual assembly tasks. As a heuristic to improve production efficiency, we optimize the sequencing of incoming orders to minimize the total count of differences in the bills of materials (BOMs) between consecutively assembled products. The resulting sequencing problem is equivalent to a specific type of an open-loop traveling salesperson problem. The matrix of distances between cities corresponds to the matrix of BOM differences, and a fixed starting city corresponds to the last product that was assembled in the previous batch of orders. To test the optimizer, we generate incoming orders with a wide range of parameterizations of a BOM difference distribution. We find that optimizing the sequencing of a large batch of incoming orders gives a significant reduction in differences in BOMs of consecutively assembled products, and gives greater benefits than optimizing smaller batches of orders in succession. The genetic algorithm has a parallelizable design and, for a batch size of a few hundred orders, executes in seconds using a personal computer with a multi-core processor. The distance matrix approach allows also to include weights specific to different types of BOM items. The plain genetic algorithm can be directly adapted to cost functions that cannot be parameterized by a distance matrix alone, for example when constraints for order due dates are included.

Key Words: Sequencing optimization, Genetic algorithm, Industry 4.0, Assembly line.

1. INTRODUCTION

The product development and manufacturing have been developing toward similar products which are assembled with customization (Lohikoski et al., 2015), (Senyo et al., 2019), and (Pawar & Sharifi, 2018). This creates challenges to maximize efficiency in an assembly line because consecutive products may require modifications in the assembly line, with an associated idle time cost away from actual assembly tasks. One trend in the product development has been going toward a rapid product development meaning shorter time used for the new product development (Jussila et al., 2020), and (Lohikoski et al., 2015) and therefore the whole product offering may change more frequently. Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) is computerized system used in manufacturing to transfer a specification of a product, i.e., bill of materials (BOM), to the finished products (Blanc et al., 2006), (Jung et al., 2016), (Kolberg & Zühlke, 2015), and (Simão et al., 2006). Even though MES provides the assembly sequence of BOMs to the assembly line, the assembly line automation system and MES are typically not fully integrated (Figay et al., 2012), and (Luftman & Brier, 1999). Furthermore, the assembly line optimization accounting for all line specific constraints cannot be done in the MES.

During the last three decades a heavily studied objective in the single-model assembly line balancing is either to minimize the number of stations or to minimize the cycle time of a predetermined number of stations (Karabati & Sayin, 2003). The trend in the manufacturing industry has been towards smart factories which are able to fulfil dynamic customer demands with high variability in small lot sizes and integrating intelligence to the automation systems (Thoben et al., 2017) and mixed-model assembly lines are needed since single-model assembly lines can't fulfil smart factory requirements.

Mixed-model assembly line in which similar products are assembled with customizations have been in the focus of research lately and the main types of mixed-model assembly problem found in literature are: the number of stations to be minimized for a given cycle time and the cycle time to be minimized for a given number of stations (Razali et al., 2019). Nevertheless, Razali et al. (2019) assume that the setup time is zero between customized products which generally does not hold as between consecutive products some changing of tools or part pallets located next to the station may be required - with an associated idle time cost away from actual assembly tasks. Boysen et al. (2009) covered five phases in the planning process of an assembly line: initial configuration of the line, master scheduling, reconfiguration planning, sequencing, and re-sequencing.

In this research, we focus on the re-sequencing phase assuming that the enterprise resource management system feeds BOMs to the assembly line in an occasional order. Our target is to reschedule them to minimize the total count of differences in the bills of materials (BOMs) between consecutively assembled products and provide a methodology for the sequencing of made-to-order products in a mixed-model assembly line. This is a typical sequencing problem aiming to optimize the total duration of operation to assemble the defined customized products (Voss et al., 2002), and (Kaisler et al., 2014).

The mixed-model assembly line optimization is analogical to the traveling salesman problem (TSP) that is a well-known problem for finding the shortest yet most efficient route for a person to take given a list of specific destinations (Hoffman & Padberg, 2001), (Applegate et al., 2006), and (Cook, 2011). In the optimization of a mixed-model assembly line the distances between cities correspond to the estimated monetary or temporal cost of adapting the assembly line between different products specified by each BOM, and a fixed starting city corresponds to the last product that was assembled in the previous batch of orders. With this analogy, it is well motivated to solve the sequencing optimization via well researched TSP approaches. Furthermore, the formulation allows high flexibility in accounting for multiple factors in the cost structure of adapting the assembly line between different products.

TSP is a nonpolynomial complete problem to solve, meaning that no efficient algorithm has been found to guarantee that the found optimum is the shortest possible and for deterministic approaches the computation times increase exponentially in relation to the amount of cities in the problem. Instead, several solutions have been developed to optimize the route close enough to the minima with an efficient algorithm. In our study, we used a genetic algorithm (GA) for solving the TSP. GAs are inspired by Darwinian evolution and are robust and applicable to multiple types of optimization problems (Contreras-Bolton & Parada, 2015).

The key concept in GA is to evaluate the multiple possible solutions for the optimization problem simultaneously and then, by "genetic modification" of the individual solutions, generate new solutions candidates to improve the solution population. The genetic modification models reproduction where parents are chosen from the solution population and their genes are passed to the child, i.e., new solution, via crossover. GA approaches with different crossover methods and fitness function formulations allow great flexibility to use GAs in many types of optimization problems, however, the efficacy of a GA also greatly depends on appropriate choices. In the TSP, the fitness of a solution candidate is the total route cost. Since GAs are highly parallelizable, implementations can have fast computation times.

We tested the algorithm in simulated experiments by generating the incoming orders with the order multiplicity and BOM distributions adjusted to match our experiences with those from a real assembly line. We aimed to demonstrate how the reduction of differences in BOMs of consecutively assembled products is attained using GA to solve TSP. We also provide the code used in this study with an open CC0 license (Niemitalo & Ekkerman, 2021).

2. METHODOLOGY

In TSP the aim is to find least costly route to visit each of N cities exactly once where the cost of traveling from city i to city j is c_{ij} (Hoffman & Padberg, 2001). We formulate the optimization of a mixed-model assembly line as a TSP by setting the cities to be the products specified by BOMs and distances between cities to be the amount of material changes between the BOMs of two cities. We assume that each product manufactured has a given time window in which it should be produced and that the optimization is run partially per time-window, e.g., planning a few days ahead. Start-city of the TSP is fixed to be the last product manufactured before the time window to be optimized. A BOM is represented as a list of M items where any list item i can represent one of K_i available materials at each station of the assembly line. Now, for example, two products P_1 and P_2 with BOMs $P_1 = [6,1,5,1,2,2,0,5,1]$ and $P_2 = [5,2,0,1,4,2,6,2,1]$ have distance $c_{1,2} = 6$ since they have different materials in six stations. Distance is always in the range from zero to M .

In the GA, individuals represent possible routes of the salesman and genes of the individual are the cities, i.e., products. Hence, an individual is representing the order of product manufacturing in the order of the genes, where the first gene, i.e., start-city, is fixed. The fitness of an individual is the sum of respective distances between cities in the order represented by the genes. To generate offspring, we used ordered crossover, where two random cut points are chosen from the first parent and the gene sequence in between is copied to the child and the remaining genes are selected from the second parent in the order of their appearance, so that no gene exists twice in the child. The crossover is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Crossover of two parents on top row producing the child on bottom row. First gene remains fixed, then a continuous sequence of genes from the first parent is inherited and the subsequent genes are inherited from the second parent in order of appearance in the parent.

Initial population is generated by sampling the genes for each individual into random order. In each generation, population vector indices are shuffled, and each individual is mated against the individual with the respective shuffled index. In the shuffling, all permutations have equal probability and the selection of the same individual twice for the crossover is allowed. Note that each individual appears once as the first parent (shuffled indices) and once as the second parent (original order). If the child has better fitness value than the second parent, i.e., lower TSP route costs, it substitutes the second parent in the next generation of the population. GA is run for a prefixed number of generations.

To test our approach, we ran simulated experiments with generated set of BOMs of materials m_i drawn from Zipf's law, defined by probability density p for a product x being $p(x) = x^{-a}/\zeta(a)$ where ζ is Riemann Zeta function and a a model parameter. We used the value of $a = 2$ in all experiments. Choice of distribution was based on the idea that often some parts are more likely to be used than the others. Only values of material $m_i \leq K_i$ were accepted and new values were drawn until this condition was satisfied. We used Python's numpy-library and its implementation of Zipf's law. Figure 2 shows the probability distribution of the Zipf's law up to ten materials. Note that we consider material 1 in station 1 being different from material 1 in station 2, etc., though this does not limit the generalizability of our work.

Figure 2. Visualization of the Zipf's law probability distribution for up to ten materials.

We ran two simulated experiments. In experiment 1, the number of products in the optimization batch was kept constant $N = 100$ but number of stations and number of materials per station varied with all combinations of values 5, 10 and 20, i.e., $M \in \{5, 10, 20\}$ and $K_i = K \in \{5, 10, 20\}$. Each combination was run for ten parallel BOM lists and their GA route costs were averaged. In experiment 2, we fixed the number of stations $M = 10$ and number of materials per stations $K_i = K = 10$ and number of products varied with $N \in \{20, 50, 100, 200\}$. With each value of N , we ran GA for ten parallel optimization BOM lists and averaged the route costs. In both experiments, GA was run for 10000 generations.

To assess the usefulness of GA optimization results to assembly line optimization, we compared the found route cost with the original random order route cost of the product BOMs and with column-wise sorted order route cost of the product BOMs. We suggest sorting as a model of the practice of an experienced human operator heuristically sequencing the order. Sorting was performed for all columns left to right with priority of sorting decreasing to right.

3. RESULTS

GA optimized route costs in experiments 1 and 2 are shown in Table 1. Based on experiment 1, the usefulness of the simple sorting approach is greatly decreased with the increase of the number of assembly stations and material options. With $M = 5$, the sorting decreased the cost to about half of the random order route cost, but with $M = 10$ the decrease was about 21% to 30% of the random order route cost and with $M = 20$ only about 11% to 14%. In experiment 2, the sorted route costs ranged from 7% and 14% lower than the random order route cost.

Table 1. Average route lengths in experiment 1 optimized with GA, column sorting.

N	M	K	GA cost	sorted cost	original cost
Experiment 1					
100	5	5	74.2	108.1	242.9
100	5	10	104.2	141.5	266.4
100	5	20	121.5	175.2	292.7
100	10	5	250.4	342.7	488.6
100	10	10	306.4	413.0	547.0
100	10	20	343.9	447.4	568.9
100	20	5	633.6	836.6	974.5
100	20	10	756.6	956.7	1088.9
100	20	20	813.3	1001.6	1129.6
Experiment 2					
20	10	10	76.1	207.4	223.3
50	10	10	162.1	516.5	559.8
100	10	10	313.8	1015.4	1145.1
200	10	10	589.7	1966.4	2277.7

As could be expected, GA performance was superior when compared with just sorting the BOMs. In experiment 1, the costs decreased an additional 19% to 31% from the sorted costs with the GA, being 28% to 69% of the

costs of the original random order cost. In experiment 2, the GA based costs were 63% to 70% lower than those of the sorted order and 66% to 74% lower than the original random order costs.

Computation times of the GA were 88 seconds for all cases in experiment 1 and 73 seconds for cases tasks in experiment 2. All computations were performed on a MSI GL63 8RC laptop with i5-8300H CPU, 8 GB of RAM and 64-bit Windows 10.

4. SUMMARY

We have demonstrated the use of the traveling salesman problem (TSP) in the optimization of mixed-model assembly lines. The optimization is based on improving production efficiency by sequencing the product lots in the way that the total idle time is minimized. The role of minimized idle time is increasing when the manufacturing trend is toward smaller production lots to fulfil customers demand. Naturally the final optimized production is case dependent where the bottlenecks in specific mixed-model assembly lines define the importance to minimize the idle time. We have assumed that the total count of differences in the bill of materials (BOM) between consecutively assembled products correspond to the total idle time and we have simulated the optimized results for different scenarios in our study.

The optimized route for TSP was computed using a genetic algorithm (GA). The results show great improvement in production line efficiency when the sequencing of products is minimizing the idle time due to adjustments between different BOMs. In total, the reduction of costs in our simulated experiments were 50 to 70 percent of what we estimate an experienced operator could achieve at best with manual sequencing. Computation times of the GA are very fast, which practically imply that the sequencing could be done in real time to include even ad-hoc orders with fast delivery requirements.

Our model, as presented here, does not include possible costs between assembly line stations with the same material, such as running out of stockpile. On the other hand, the model is easily adjustable to account for different types of costs, e.g., real measured time to change tools or part ballets and part ballet changes when needed within the same material. Nonetheless, we conclude that even sole reduction of material changes greatly increases the efficiency of the assembly line. Further research is suggested to deepen the understanding of the idle time importance in different types of mixed-model assembly line setups and to validate the results in real world scenarios.

The genetic algorithm source code written in C++ is available at Niemitalo & Ekkerman (2021) and is licensed with the CC0 license.

5. REFERENCES

Applegate, D., Bixby, R. E., Chvatal, V., & Cook, W. (2006). *The Traveling Salesman Problem: A Computational Study*. Princeton University Press, Princeton.

Blanc, P., Demongodin, I., & Castagna, P. (2006). A Holonic Approach For Manufacturing Control: An Industrial Application. *Information Control Problems in Manufacturing 2006*, 389–394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-008044654-7/50198-9>

Boysen, N., Fliender, M., & Scholl, M. (2009). Production planning of mixed-model assembly lines: overview and extensions. *Production Planning & Control*, 20(5). <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09537280903011626>

Contreras-Bolton, C., & Parada, V. (2015). Automatic Combination of Operators in a Genetic Algorithm to Solve the Traveling Salesman Problem. *Public Library of Science*, 10(9).

Cook, W. (2011). In Pursuit of the Salesman: Mathematics at the Limits of Computation. Princeton University Press, Princeton.

Figay, N., Ghodous, P., Khalfallah, M., & Barhamgi, M. (2012). Interoperability framework for dynamic manufacturing networks. *Computers in Industry*, 63(8), 749–755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2012.08.008>

Hoffman, K. L., & Padberg, M. (2001). Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) Traveling salesman problem. *Encyclopedia of Operations Research and Management Science*, 3(1), 849–853. https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-0611-X_1068

Jung, K., Kulvatunyou, B., Choi, S., & Brundage, M. P. (2016). An overview of a smart manufacturing system readiness assessment. *IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology*, 488, 705–712. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51133-7_83

Jussila, J., Raitanen, J., Partanen, A., Tuomela, V., Siipola, V., & Kunnari, I. (2020). Rapid Product Development in University-Industry Collaboration: Case Study of a Smart Design Project. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 10(3).

Kaisler, S. H., Espinosa, J. A., Armour, F., & Money, W. H. (2014). Advanced Analytics--Issues and Challenges in a Global Environment. *47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 729–738.

Karabati, S., & Sayin, S. (2003). Assembly line balancing in a mixed-model sequencing environment with synchronous transfers. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 149(2), 417–429. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217\(02\)00764-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217(02)00764-6)

Kolberg, D., & Zühlke, D. (2015). Lean Automation enabled by Industry 4.0 Technologies. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 28(3), 1870–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2015.06.359>

Lohikoski, P., Kujala, J., Härkönen, J., Haapasalo, H., & Muhos, M. (2015). Enhancing Communication Practices in Virtual New Product Development Projects. *International Journal of Innovation in the Digital Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijide.2015100102>

Luftman, J., & Brier, T. (1999). Achieving and Sustaining Business-IT Alignment. *California Management Review*, 42(1), 109–122. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41166021>

Niemitalo, O., & Ekkerman, G. (2021). assembly-line-sequencing-ga. <https://github.com/hamk-uas/assembly-line-sequencing-ga>

Pawar, K. S., & Sharifi, S. (2018). Physical and virtual collaboration in new product development: A comparative analysis. 2017 International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation: Engineering, Technology and Innovation Management Beyond 2020: New Challenges, New Approaches, ICE/ITMC 2017 - Proceedings, 2018-Janua, 997–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICE.2017.8279990>

Razali, M. M., Kamarudin, N. H., Mohd Fadzil, M. F. F., & Mohd Rose, A. N. (2019). Recent trend in mixed-model assembly line balancing optimization using soft computing approaches. *Engineering Computations (Swansea, Wales)*, 36(2), 622–645. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EC-05-2018-0205>

Senyo, P. K., Liu, K., & Effah, J. (2019). Digital business ecosystem: Literature review and a framework for future research. *International Journal of Information Management*, 47(June 2018), 52–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.01.002>

Simão, J. M., Stadzisz, P. C., & Morel, G. (2006). Manufacturing execution systems for customized production. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 179(1–3), 268–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2006.03.064>

Thoben, K. D., Wiesner, S. A., & Wuest, T. (2017). “Industrie 4.0” and smart manufacturing-a review of research issues and application examples. *International Journal of Automation Technology*, 11(1), 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.20965/ijat.2017.p0004>

Voss, C., Tsikriktsis, N., & Frohlich, M. (2002). Case research in operations management. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 22(2), 195–219. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443570210414329>